

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for injector cleaning of GC Q – Exactive

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Summary

This section describes cleaning the QC injector body. Perform this operation when a more efficient cleaning of the injector body is needed. This operation must be performed after measurement of derivatized samples and before measurement nonderivatized samples (derivatization agents adheres to the injector body/analytical column).

IMPORTANT

- Always place the components on a clean, lint-free surface (aluminium foil)
- Use a new pair of lint-and powder-free gloves before starting each removal and cleaning
- When turning Off the GC: first turn off the temperature and then turn off the carrier gas flow
- When turning ON the GC: first turn on the carrier gas flow and then the temperature

NOTE: Use acetone for removing derivatization agents

NOTE: Turning ON/OF GC in reverse order may cause column destroy

Preparing GC for maintenance

Turn the oven, injector to a room temperature and then turn off the carrier gas flow

- 1) Put the GC in standby condition
- 2) Turn off the temperature, wait until is the temperature at least ~ 60°C (Go to Touch Screen Main Menu > Maintenance > Front (SSL) > Cool this zone > Yes > Begin Cooldown)

- 3) Turn the carrier gas flow of front inlet Off (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (SSL) > Column flow > Off)

To remove the injector body

Figure 1. Injector components

Figure 2. Injector Body cleaning

- 4) Open the module flap cover
- 5) Unscrew the Ring Nut
- 6) Remove the septum holder and using tweezers remove the old liner with liner seal (ring)
- 7) Unscrew the Terminal fitting for Capillary Column, then remove the analytical column/guard column with its ferrule from the bottom of the injector
- 8) Unscrew the Retaining Nut with the Washer and the Base Seal
- 9) Unscrew Injector Body Fixing Screws and remove Injector Body with Body Head Internal O – ring and Body Head External O – ring

To clean injector body

- 10) Use tweezers to place the Injector Body and Retaining Nut to a beaker with methanol/acetone 50:50 (v/v) and sonicate for 15 minutes
- 11) Transfer the injector body and Retaining Nut (with tweezers) to a beaker with toluene and sonicate for 15 minutes
- 12) Transfer the injector body and Retaining Nut (with tweezers) to a beaker with methanol/acetone 50:50 (v/v) and sonicate for 15 minutes
- 13) Remove with tweezers from the solvent and dry it with an inert gas
- 14) Reinstall new Body Head Internal O – ring and Body Head External O – ring
- 15) Using tweezers, insert new Body Head Internal O – ring and Body Head External O – ring
- 16) Reinstall and fix the Injector Body into its housing by screwing the two fixing screws
- 17) Reinstall the Retaining Nut (use a new Washer and Base Seal)
- 18) Reinstall the analytical column/guard column
- 19) Take new liner (hold only the upper part of the liner) and put liner seal (ring) to the liner
- 20) Gently insert new liner with liner seal (ring) to the injector and push it gently towards the bottom of the injector. (Be careful not to break the glass liner)

21) Close the septum holder. Screw and gently tighten the right nut

22) Close the module flap cover

To restore temperatures and gas flow

23) Turn on the temperature (Maintenance > Front (SSL) > Cool this zone > No >

Restore temperatures

24) Wait minimum 30 minutes for the stabilization system